

PAROMA-MED

Privacy Aware and Privacy Preserving
Distributed and Robust Machine Learning

PAROMA-MED will develop, validate and evaluate a platform - based hybrid-cloud delivery framework for privacy- and security-assured services and applications in federative cross-border environments.

36
Months of
Research

9
Consortium
Partners

€4.3M
Costs & EU
Funding

1 Federation Marketplace & Automatic Attestation

Develop a federation marketplace supported by a platform service for the automatic attestation of federation partners and for their inclusion in the service and data provider catalogue.

2 Developer-Friendly Platform & Policy Framework

Develop a user-friendly platform service and policy framework to support the developers in defining high-level applications and privacy & security requirements, including the right to be forgotten.

3 Federated Identity & Zero Trust Access Management

Develop federative identity management solution and an access management solution based on zero trust principles.

4 Secure & Privacy-Preserving Networking

Develop a secure and privacy-preserving networking solution for flexible access over the internet.

5 Trusted Execution Environments with Hardware Security

Develop software defined trusted execution environments that exploit hardware isolation and security capabilities.

6 Cloud-Native Open-Source Solutions

Implement open-source cloud-native solutions, to support efficiency and scalability

7 Healthcare Use Case Validation

Validate and evaluate the framework by the development of a comprehensive use case with real users in the healthcare sector.

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